

Astrophysical Preservation of Terrestrial Life on Mars Through a Sphericalist, Esoteric Futurist Approach

Volume Two of Two

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of
Liverpool John Moores University for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy
August 2024

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Introduction

This transdisciplinary research is presented in two volumes as a means of presenting the information and research in a structured and accessible format. Whereas Volume One consists of the main body of the thesis, the bibliography and appendices, Volume Two presents the Praxis elements of the thesis. These include the sonic creative practice, incorporating a QR code link to the album *Beyond The Musical Divide* on Apple Music, track listings with track durations, copyright information, publishing information, sleeve notes and lyrics.

Volume Two of the thesis also incorporates visual copies of the paintings, a full presentation of the CD package artwork and layout design, as well as 3D renderings of the post terrestrial biological salvage preserve designs. This acts as both a counterbalance to the information that details the sonic praxis, whilst clarifying how the musical and visual praxis are symbiotically interconnected with each being expressed in the other. This, in turn, provides another clear example of how the praxis relates and integrates with the overall methodological original contribution to knowledge this thesis provides, SEF, by emphasising the interconnected, inter-subject compatibility and systemic interchangeability that is central to the holistic, abstracted logic this methodology illustrates and informs.

Sonic Creative Practice

Beyond The Musical Divide
A VR Electronic Symphony in Three Movements

CD Hyperlink & QR Code

<https://music.apple.com/us/artist/vin-Førde/1707980261>

CD Tracklist & Durations

1. Introduction: Ignorance is No Longer Bliss 09:27
2. First Movement: Mantra of Hubris 06:00
3. Patterns of Courage 04:29
4. Patterns of Hope 04:23
5. Arrangements of Awareness 03:48
6. Second Movement: Anomalies 02: 28
7. Moments Unnamed 03:59
8. Anomalies and Duplicity 07:53
9. Third Movement: Fallen Doctrines 09:59
10. Patterns of Emptiness 03:49
11. Mantra of Nemesis 07:01
12. The Fate of Ares 08:52
13. Coda: Liberation and Reconciliation 05:01

Album Copyright

Music by Vin Førde.

Duration: 73 minutes 42 seconds.

All instruments and vocals performed by Vin Førde.

VR instruments: Oorgan, Board, Wharp, Wavemin, Empads, Clustr & VR microphone.

Composed, arranged and produced by Vin Førde

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The following 100% open source/public domain NASA audio samples were used in this recording:

Track 1

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones- Enceladus Hiss audio 256 kbps* [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 7 July 2022 for use in 'Ignorance is No Longer Bliss']. © NASA

Track 5

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones-584795main_saturn_radio_waves*. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 3 July 2022 for use in 'Arrangements of Awareness']. © NASA

Track 6

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones- Enceladus Hiss audio 256 kbps*. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 7 July 2022 for use in 'Anomalies']. © NASA

Track 7

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones- e2-Wave-Ganymede-flyby_compressed* [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 7 July 2022 for use in 'Moments Unnamed']. © NASA

Track 8

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones- Enceladus Hiss audio 256 kbps; KIC7671081B*. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 7 July 2022 for use in 'Anomalies and Duplicity']. © NASA

Track 9

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones-Sounds of Enceladus Radar Echoes from Titan's Surface*. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 2 July 2022 for use in 'Fallen Doctrines']. © NASA

Track 11

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones-Kepler: Star KIC7671081B Light Curve Waves to Sound*. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 4 July 2022 for use in 'Mantra of Nemesis']. © NASA

Track 12

Wilson, J. (2015). *Audio and Ringtones- First Sounds of Mars and 693857main_emfisis_chorus_1*. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 4 July 2022 for use in 'The Fate of Ares']. © NASA

Sleeve Notes

Beyond the Musical Divide

The recordings contained on this CD were composed and performed as part my PhD research. This research focused on the topic of Mars and ways of preventing ecocide through the design and construction of a post-terrestrial biological salvage preserve, which could be built on the red planet later this century. My research also proposes a new form of socio-political-economic application that could be utilised to engender a new form of global civilisation. In turn, this could safeguard the continuity of terrestrial life, whilst interlinking harmoniously with AI operations within the post-terrestrial biological salvage preserve, and possible future human colonies on Mars. I have named this transdisciplinary application, spherical esoteric futurism (SEF).

The music is composed and produced in virtual reality using Meta Quest 2. Beyond the Musical Divide is a 13-track experimental symphonic electronica album composed, performed, arranged, produced, and recorded entirely in virtual reality. This album contains a three-movement electronic symphony replete with an introduction and a coda. Beyond The Musical Divide was produced using the first VR music production studio, Interactive AB/Fast Travel Games AB's, Virtuoso.

These musical compositions were made in response to my 11 piece painting suite that I had completed shortly before discovering Virtuoso. This painting suite is also organised into three sections of 3, 5, and 3 paintings respectively. They present the environmental history, present, and possible future of Mars. Billions of years ago, Mars was much like how the Earth is now. Mars almost certainly once had life, and may still have today. However, through calamitous environmental processes, Mars lost a significant portion of its atmosphere and magnetic field, transforming it into the cold desert world observed now. The cosmological history and present condition of Mars acts as a cautionary tale mirroring the ecological devastation humans are inflicting upon Earth, in its relentless pursuit of material gain, consumption, and convenience.

Beyond The Musical Divide is an exploration of the subject matter of my research, a means of emotionally, creatively, and intellectually investigating the numerous

aspects of my project and the current, changing age, where previously dismissed esoteric subjects such as UAPs, life after death, AI consciousness, cryptozoology, and extraterrestrial life are now being given serious scientific study. Virtual reality is an expansive tool that enabled me to produce and record this music. In this virtual setting, I became both composer and virtual musician, performing on instruments that had been invented specifically for the purpose of VR composition.

At the heart of this symphony is the theme of life, death, and rebirth. Our current way of life must die so that our civilisation can be reborn and redesigned. It is proposed that this process can be made possible through SEF, and the multifarious interconnectivity it engenders and illuminates psychologically, emotionally, physically, sociologically, politically, scientifically, and spiritually. The integration of SEF as a method of transforming terrestrial civilisation will yield a sustainable future, rather than allowing the perpetuation of conventional solutions that ultimately, only beget the continuation of conventional problems. Therefore, *Beyond The Musical Divide* is the sonic expression of SEF, and the opportunity humanity currently has to prevent a future where virtually all terrestrial life has been destroyed, and Earth closely resembles Mars.

Beyond The Musical Divide Lyrics

Ignorance Is No Longer Bliss

All we have and all we know,
And all we hold is what we show,
Absolom, it will not ever cease,
Redemption it will now preach,
Peremption that we do seek,
Now we leave you to be,
All the sounds of lies and time,
Everything they teach,

Is this all, that we have left?

(repeats once)

Ignorance is no longer bliss,
Ignorance is no longer bliss,

All we saw, all we know,
Lick the honey and the bloodied snow,
Ignorance taught,
In the cold and the time,
As price has found,
An illusion that has run aground,

Brought its lies and silent scream,
Breaking actual lives and law,
Ignorance is no longer bliss,

Is this all, that we have left?

Ignorance is no longer bliss,
Ignorance is no longer bliss,

All we have and all we know,
And all we hold is what we show,
Absolom, it will not ever cease,
Redemption it will now preach,
Peremption that we do seek,
Now we bet you will be,
All the sounds of lies and time,
Everything they teach,

All we saw, all we know,
Lick the honey and the bloodied snow,
Ignorance taught,
In the cold and the time,
As price has found,
An illusion that has run aground,
Brought its lies and silent scream,
Breaking ruined lives and law,

All we have and all we know,

And all we hold is what we show,
Absolom, it will not ever cease,
Redemption it will now preach,
Peremption that we do seek,
Now we leave you to be,
All the sounds of lies and time,
Everything they teach,
Is this all, that we have left?

Patterns of Hope

So now, I go, upon, the heart,
The sound, of life, it beats the start,
And I will hold you on, cradles of the stars,
And I will hold you on, all the joys of life.

(Repeated)

Arrangements of Awareness

In the heart, far away from here,
In the snow, we take and grow from fear,
And I will see you here with me,
I will have your heart so true, so near,

Let me see,
Your heart so true,
And in our truce,
You shall be renewed, renewed!
In the heart, far away from here,
In the snow, we take and grow from fear,
And now I will see you take the hand,
Let me find your heart so clear from fear,

Let me see,
Your heart so true,
And in our truce,
You shall be renewed, renewed!

In the heart, far away from here,
In the snow, we take and grow from fear... from fear,
And I will see you here with me,
I will have your heart so true, so near.

Fallen Doctrines

You and I, you and I, will never die, never die!

You and I, you and I, will never die, never die!

You and I, you and I, will never die, never die!

You and I, you and I, will never die, never die!

We now want to die,

As the Gods will cry,

We turn the key,

We turn the key,

In everything we choose to be...

Fallen doctrines,

It's fallen doctrines,

It's fallen doctrines,

It's fallen doctrines,

Ignorance, deception, horror and arrogance,

Life is, a reflection, of everything we choose to be,

Fallen Doctrines,

It's fallen doctrines,

It's fallen doctrines,

It's fallen doctrines,

Ignorance, deception, horror and arrogance,

Life is a reflection.

Patterns of Emptiness

Bleeding, so true,
Is this all we have to deny?

Patterns of emptiness,

After all, sunrise,

Patterns of emptiness,

Take me from this pit of ice,
In all, that I, hold on,
The destruction of time,

Patterns of emptiness fill my heart,
Even though we know which will depart,
Destruction has bled that long into,
The horror of absolute souls run through,
Orienting empty paths,
Patterns of emptiness,

(Repeats twice)

Patterns of emptiness,

Patterns of emptiness fill my heart,
Even though we know which will depart,
Destruction has bled that long into,

The horror of absolute souls run through,

Patterns of emptiness,

Patterns of emptiness.

Visual Creative Practice

PhD Paintings

Fig. a
Vincent Førde
Martian Cliff Face with Gold Embankment (2018)
Acrylic on Canvas
35.5 x 49 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. b
Vincent Førde
Martian Frozen Desert Including both Highland and Lowland Regions (2019)
Acrylic on Canvas
60.96 x 76.2 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. c
Vincent Førde
Martian Landscape Possible Basalt Desert with Sand Glacial Formations (2019)
Acrylic on Canvas
60.96 x 76.2 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. d
Vincent Førde
Undiscerned Martian Landscape Formation (2020)
Acrylic on Canvas
27.3 x 36.5 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. e
Vincent Førde
Complex Multifaceted Mineral Field (2021)
48 x 59.5 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. f
Vincent Førde
Ancient Martian Northern Hemisphere Seascape No#1 (2022)
Acrylic on Canvas
35.5 x 116 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. g
Vincent Førde
Ancient Martian Northern Hemisphere Seascape No#2 (2019)
Acrylic on Canvas
45 x 137 cm
Private Collection

Fig. h
Vincent Førde
Ancient Martian Ice Mountain Seascape (2019)
Acrylic on Canvas
45 x 137 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. i
Vincent Førde
Terraforming and The Domed City (2022)
Acrylic on Canvas
27.3 x 36.5 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. j
Vincent Førde
Progression of The Domed City (2022)
Acrylic on Canvas
30.5 x 36.5 cm
Collection of The Artist

Fig. k
Vincent Førde
Release of The Domed City (2022)
Acrylic on Canvas
30.5 x 36.5 cm
Collection of The Artist

Beyond The Music Divide CD Package

Fig. 1

Fig. m

Vin Førde
Beyond The Musical Divide

Composed, arranged and produced by Vin Førde
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Fig. n

Vin Forde
Beyond The Musical Divide

Vin Forde Beyond The Musical Divide VI#017

Vin Forde
Beyond The Musical Divide

1. Introduction: Aggravance is No Longer Bliss 09:27
2. First Movement: Matters of Habit 06:10
3. Patterns of Change 04:29
4. Patterns of Hope 04:23
5. Arrangements of Awareness 03:48
6. Second Movement: Anomalies 02:28
7. Moments Unmistakable 04:59
8. Anomalies and Duplcity 07:53
9. Third Movement: Ethical Encumbrances 09:39
10. Patterns of Emptiness 03:59
11. Matters of Sense 07:04
12. The Fate of Aes 08:52
13. Gothic Observation and Reconciliation 05:01

Contents arranged and produced by Vin Forde
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Fig. o

Fig. p

Vin Førde
Beyond The Musical Divide

Fig. q

Vin Førde
Beyond The Musical Divide

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Fig. s

Fig. t

Music by Vin Førdø.

Duration: 73 minutes 42 seconds.

All instruments and vocals performed by Vin Førdø.

VR instruments: Oorgan, Board, Wharp, Wavemin, Eimpads, Clustr & VR microphone.

All paintings by Vin Førdø.

Composed, arranged and produced by Vin Førdø

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<https://vinfodoe.bandcamp.com/album/beyond-the-musical-divide>

The following open source/public domain NASA audio samples were used in this recording:

Track 1
Wilson, J. (2015). Audio and Ringtones-Enceladus Hiss audio 256 kbps [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 7 July 2022 for use in 'Ignorance is No Longer Bliss']. © NASA

Track 5
Wilson, J. (2015). Audio and Ringtones-584795main_saturn_radio_waves. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 3 July 2022 for use in 'Arrangements of Awareness']. © NASA

Track 6
Wilson, J. (2015). Audio and Ringtones-Enceladus Hiss audio 256 kbps. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 7 July 2022 for use in 'Anomalies']. © NASA

Track 7
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Track 8
Wilson, J. (2015). Audio and Ringtones- Enceladus Hiss audio 256 kbps: KIC7671081B. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 7 July 2022 for use in 'Anomalies and Duplicity']. © NASA

Track 9
Wilson, J. (2015). Audio and Ringtones-Sounds of Enceladus Radar Echoes from Titan's Surface. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 2 July 2022 for use in 'Fallen Doctrines']. © NASA

Track 11
Wilson, J. (2015). Audio and Ringtones-Kepler: Star KIC7671081B Light Curve Waves to Sound. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 4 July 2022 for use in 'Mantra of Nemesis']. © NASA

Track 12
Wilson, J. (2015). Audio and Ringtones-First Sounds of Mars and 693857main_emfisis_chorus_1. [online] NASA. Available at: <https://www.nasa.gov/connect/sounds/index.html>. [Accessed 4 July 2022 for use in 'The Fate of Ares']. © NASA

Fig. u

Fig. v

Post Terrestrial Biological Salvage Preserve Designs

Design 1

20,000 x 25,000 feet
Fig. w (Førde, 2020)

Design 2

20,000 x 20,000 feet
Fig. x (Førde, 2020)

20,000 x 20,000 feet
Fig. y (Førde, 2020)

Design 3

10,000 feet x 20,000 feet
Fig. z (Førde, 2020)

2021/09/03 08:22:06

10,000 feet x 20,000 feet
Fig. aa (Førde, 2020)

Final Design

20,000 feet x 20,000 feet ~ 100 acres
Fig. bb (Førde, 2020)

20,000 feet x 20,000 feet ~ 100 acres
Fig. cc (Førde, 2020)

The SEF Blueprint: The Sphericalist Manifesto

At the core of this project, and one of the principle outputs of the SEF methodology, is a political ideology to redesign and reboot humanity psychologically, emotionally, and organisationally. Change is not to be feared. Change is essential. Without change, life is impossible. Change is adaptation. Survival is possible because of adaptation. Evolution is a by-product of adaptation. Any species that can't or willingly refuses to adapt to its environment, or, in the case of humans, an environment of its own creation, dies. An organism and even an entire universe exists and continues to exist through the complex interplay of multifarious, interrelated, reactive factors, all of which are in constant flux, yet ephemeral and mysterious. To disregard this inexorable truth of the universe is to disregard the continuity of one's presence within such.

Arguably, the principle foundations of any civilisation are reflective cognition, analytical thinking, creative expression, and cooperation. Mass collaboration to create cyclical behavioural feedback systems (i.e., social roles/jobs/classes/castes/industry), is not singular to humanity. One of the key sources for humanity's destruction of the environment is the delusion that it is the paramount expression of intelligent life. Ironically, there is nothing intelligent in destroying one's environment and future survival for material acquisition, dominance over members of one's own species, and convenience. A discursive study of the self-organisation of species that operate methods of construction as part of their socialisation (bees/termites/beavers), as well as those that administer

medication to their members, reveals the crux of human exceptionalism to be erroneous.

Further bipedal species have been discovered that counter human exceptionalism, in regards to having developed language, cultural rituals, art, tools, and complex means of interaction. These include the giant 7 - 8 foot Denisovans, who lived in modern day Russia 160,000 years ago, Homo floresiensis, a hobbit-like people who lived in Indonesia up to 50,000 years ago, and Neanderthals, who lived in Europe up to 40,000 years ago, and still survive within human DNA (Hendry, 2018; Chetan-Welsh and Hendry, n.d.; Warren, 2019).

In spring 2024, biologists in Indonesia observed targeted botanical self-medication practices in a male Sumatran orangutan, named Rakus (www.mpg.de, n.d.). After sustaining a brutal, gouging facial wound, Rakus ate, repeatedly applied sap, and covered his wound with a climbing plant, Akar Kuning (*Fibraurea tinctoria*), that possesses analgesic and antipyretic properties and is used in traditional medicine to treat diseases such as malaria (www.mpg.de, n.d.).

Cognitive and evolutionary biologists from the Max Planck Institute of Animal Behaviour in Konstanz, Germany, Caroline Schuppli and Isabelle Laumer, undertook the study at the Suaq Balimbing conservation research site in Indonesia (www.mpg.de, n.d.). The scientific team stated that: 'analyses of plant chemical compounds show the presence of furanoditerpenoids and protoberberine alkaloids, which are known to have antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-fungal, antioxidant, and other biological activities of relevance to wound healing'

(www.mpg.de, n.d.). Somehow, Sumatran orangutans acquired knowledge of this plants medicinal properties and saw fit to administer it as medicine, all without the need for built environments and institutionalised, myopic academic constructs.

One species that is central to both illustrating the folly concerning human exceptionalism, as well as illuminating one of the primary natural inspirations for sphericalism as a social organisational doctrine, is ants. Ants have a hierarchy (including royalty), maintain professions with role promotion (careers), operate agriculture and animal husbandry, educate their youth, care for their disabled and elderly, bury their dead, and express honour and deep respect for bees, giving them ceremonial funerals (www.youtube.com, n.d.; psychologytoday.com, n.d.). Ants have survived for 100 million years, operate a defensive guard system (military), and function sustainably, with most colonies generally enhancing their environment (www.youtube.com, n.d.; psychologytoday.com, n.d.).

Fire ants create floating rafts made of their colony to ensure its survival, with changes in role so no individual drowns (Weisberger, M, 2021). Ants protect their colony in times of infection through operating social distancing (without the need for enforcement of such logical and altruistic behaviour). Ants even create vaccines and initiate vaccination procedures to administer them throughout their society (psychologytoday.com, n.d.; Fritsche, 2021). Ant social megastructures can grow to 50 square metres, maintain built-in ventilation design features, side roads, living quarters, and operate many levels, sometimes reaching down 8 metres into the Earth (Fritsche, 2021). In reference to the size of an ant, such a megastructure is the engineering equivalent of Manhattan.

Edward O. Wilson, world-renowned ant researcher, once stated that, 'if all mankind were to disappear, the world would regenerate back to the rich state of equilibrium that existed ten thousand years ago. If insects were to vanish, the environment would collapse into chaos' (Earth911, 2023). Regarding social organisation, cooperation, and sustainable practices, ants, not humans, are the most advanced species on Earth. Ant civilisation is akin to subterranean human civilisation 2,700 years ago, an example being Derinkuyu, in Nevşehir Province, Turkey, where humanity lived in relative harmony with creation, and not against it. On the contrary, operating counter to the harmonious equilibrium of nature is a destructive, parasitic trait modern society has uniquely and voraciously achieved.

In terms of sustainable design, cooperation, social and interpersonal cohesion, ant society is far more advanced than current human civilisation. Consequently, it is the dynamics and subtle complexities of ant civilisation where sphericalism acquires its immediate sociological inspiration from. However, the sphericalist doctrine and its resulting society are not emulations of ant society, as ant civilisation is at times war-like and, on relatively rare occasion, deleterious to the overall harmony of its environment (Fritsche, 2021). Sphericalism seeks to observe and be informed by the greatest manifestations of organised terrestrial life, yet also seeks to engender each sphericalist practitioner, and the society collectively formed by all these adepts, to become more than the combined elements and features of such. Sphericalism is harmonious progress in action.

Civilisation formed through the confluence of art and science. Without art, there is no fulcrum through which imagination can be expressed. Without science, there is no logical framework, no guiding path to maintain objective focus. Art is the

foundation and structural material, whilst science is the architectural design. Prior to capitalism, when settlements were smaller, cooperation was not admirable, it was essential for survival. Environments improved, populations increased, mechanisation developed, coinage-based economies grew, technology advanced, and humans became separatists to nature. Sphericalism counters this process (see chapter one). Sphericalism is sustainability.

Ordered abstraction is fundamental to the connection between creativity and science. Modern scientific research is revealing how abstract and dependant on consciousness the universe appears to be, whilst maintaining intricate fractal forms that underpin the obvious mathematical design of creation. Examples include the Fibonacci sequence, the Golden Ratio, fractals, hexagons, concentric circles, chaos theory, symmetry, natural oscillatory systems, and morphogenesis (see the following illustrations). Unfortunately, this mathematical harmony is being unbalanced by the rapacious and perfidious activities and machinations of humanity.

Fig. dd: *The Fibonacci Sequence*
(Robert Lamb, 2023)

Fig. ee: Raft Bubbles: Hexagons in Nature
(mathgeekmama.com, 2019)

Fig. ff: *The Fibonacci Sequence*
(scientia73.com, 2022)

Fig. gg: Honeycomb Tessellation of Hexagons: Hexagons in Nature
(mathgeekmama.com, 2019)

Fig. hh: Concentric Circles in Nature
(mathgeekmama.com, 2019)

Fig. ii: Orb Weaving Spider Web
(bugguide.net, 2019)

<p>Star fish</p>			
<p>Flower</p>			
<p>Crystal structure</p>			

Fig. jj: Examples of Symmetry & Visual Oscillation in Nature
(Vopson, 2023)

Fig. kk:
Turing Models Depicting Pattern Formation
(owlcation.com, 2023)

Fig. ll: Comparisons of Micro and Macro Elements in Universal Design/Sacred Geometry
(The Awakened State, 2016)

Sphericalist art and music are based on controlled abstraction and logic. Consequently, a sphericalist creation can never lose touch with the guiding principles of science, as this prevents it from becoming vacuous, divisive, or propagandist. Likewise, a sphericalist scientific investigation must never lose touch with the open mindedness and impartiality that is instilled within art. This engenders an open receptivity to all evidence pertaining to any scientific pursuit.

Civilisation is a manifestation of the confluence between art and science (creative/logical reasoning). Civilisation is the manifestation of the consciousnesses of all those who participate and have participated in it. Consciousness observes probability. Probability waves collapse through the quantum observer effect to manifest reality and experience. Reality is perceived through visual, sonic, emotional, and thought constructs, all of which connect to geometry. The problem and resolution of existence, is geometry.

Arguably, the sphere is the perfect geometric form. There is an active relationship between SEF, quaternion number system, and hypersphere 4D Euclidean geometrics, as these mathematical concepts correspond to the 4D conceptualisation at the core of SEF ontological abstraction. Mathematicians have postulated that time is the fourth dimension (New Scientist, 2019). Time has been represented as a conical form, a line, or a circle (Quora, n.d.). All three fit within a sphere. The sphere is the geometric symbolisation of the oneness of the interlinked totality of reality.

Sacred geometry is composed of dominant forms. All fit within a sphere with at least two or more points connecting within such, including the 'Tree of Life' said

to contain all the patterns of creation. The Fibonacci sequence, Phi, and Pi have relationships with the geometry of a sphere (Mathematics Stack Exchange, n.d.). Additionally, the Möbius Strip, which represents infinity, can be interpolated with a sphere (www.youtube.com, n.d.).

Consequently, the universe can be ontologically symbolised by the sphere. Within a sphere, all localities are connected, thus, there is no (isolated) locality. There is no point of separation or discontinuity between every aspect of a sphere, internally, or in regards to its surface and that which orbits it. Through mentally perceiving human experience/knowledge and the unknown aspects of the universe in an interconnected, spherical way, divisionism/materialism are revealed as illusionary constructs of an uninformed or recalcitrant, egoistic state of consciousness. Sphericalism runs through every facet of this thesis and PhD. This thesis is the first example of a sphericalist investigation, and like all future investigations of this kind, every facet of it naturally leads to the potential creation of a sphericalist perspective, and potentially, a sphericalist civilisation (see chapter one).

The Nine Phases of Spherical Esoteric Futurism (SEF):

- 1) Human induced climate change has wrought a state of global ecological collapse aka, the Anthropocene epoch.
- 2) The Anthropocene Ecological Collapse is the most critical existential emergency humanity currently faces, and must be addressed through a highly focused collective immediacy to prevent ecocide.
- 3) Conventional problems are manifested through divisionist propensities abject to the intrinsic interconnection of the feasibly holographic, consciousness influenced, quantum and mathematical universal system.

- 4) Conventional solutions only beget the eventual continuation of conventional problems, of which the Anthropocene is the current conceptual embodiment.
- 5) Current human civilisation is analogous to a program running on an incompatible system. Consequently, the program has become auto-cannibalistic, and the natural system is crashing.
- 6) A new holistic socio-economic-political psychology encompassing art, science, and esoteric knowledge is required to resolve this existential catastrophe.
- 7) Spherical Esoteric Futurism (SEF) is the transdisciplinary application that will induce this transformation in human psychology, and thus, human organisation, to engender a sustainable system.
- 8) Creative application of the SEF framework has determined that, to ensure the survival of Earth originated life, a post terrestrial biological salvage reserve must be constructed on Mars, operated by an advanced AIOS, in the absence of humans.
- 9) The application of SEF can engender a positive creative, psychological feedback loop between AI life preserving isolated operations on Mars, future human communities on Mars, and terrestrial civilisation, enhancing societal transformation from divisionist propensities to harmonious operational designs.